

DEVELOPMENT OF CHATBOT USING AI/ML TECHNOLOGIES

*A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the
requirement for the award of the degree of*

BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY

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This is to certify that the project titled **DEVELOPMENT OF CHATBOT USING ML TECHNOLOGY** is a bona fide record of the work done by *Maisnam Akash Singh (2001CS0214) & Dorenjit Haorokcham (2001CS0232)* submitted to Manipur Technical University Imphal, Manipur during the academic year 2020-2024, in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science & Engineering Department. The contents of this report, in full or in parts, have not been submitted to any other Institution or University for the award of any degree or diploma.

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis entitled **DEVELOPMENT OF CHATBOT USING ML TECHNOLOGY** submitted in partial fulfilment of the degree of Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science & Engineering is a record of original work carried out by me under the supervision of **Mr. Chiranjiv Chingangbam** and has not formed the basis for the award of any other degree or diploma, in this or any other Institution or University. In keeping with the ethical practice in reporting scientific information, due acknowledgements have been made wherever the findings of others have been cited.

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancements in artificial intelligence and natural language processing have significantly transformed human-computer interactions. This thesis presents the design, development, and evaluation of an intelligent chatbot capable of engaging in natural and meaningful conversations with users. The chatbot leverages state-of-the-art deep learning techniques, including transformer-based architectures, to understand and generate human-like responses.

Key contributions of this research include the implementation of a context-aware conversational model that can maintain coherent dialogue over extended interactions. The chatbot's performance is evaluated through both automated metrics and user studies, demonstrating its effectiveness in various applications such as customer service, mental health support, and educational assistance. Additionally, ethical considerations and potential biases in chatbot responses are examined to ensure the responsible deployment of this technology.

The findings of this thesis highlight the potential of intelligent chatbots to enhance user experience and provide valuable insights for future developments in conversational AI.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter will introduce briefly a definition of chatbot. Afterwards, a brief history of the field of conversational agents will be recalled in section 1.3. Finally, it will also motivate the need for further developments in chatbots by referencing recent surveys conducted on this subject.

1.1 Chatbot: Definition

According to the Oxford English Dictionary, a chatbot is defined as follows: chatbot (n.): A computer program designed to simulate conversation with human users, especially over the Internet.

In the scientific literature, chatbots are more formally referred to as conversational agents. In the context of this document, the terms chatbot/conversational agent will be used interchangeably.

The underlying principle of every chatbot is to interact with a human user (in most cases) via text messages and behave as though it were capable of understanding the conversation and reply to the user appropriately. The origin of computers conversing with humans is as old as the field of computer Science itself. Indeed, Alan Turing defined a simple test referred to now as the Turing test back in 1950 where a human judge would have to predict if the entity, they are communicating with via text is a computer program or not. However, this test's ambition is much greater than the usual use case of chatbots; the main difference being that the domain knowledge of a chatbot is narrow whereas the Turing test assumes one can talk about any topic with the agent. This helps during the design of conversational agents as they are not required to have a (potentially) infinite domain knowledge and can, as such, focus on certain very specific topics such as for instance helping users book a table at a restaurant.

Furthermore, another general assumption chatbot designers bear in mind is that users typically have a goal they want to achieve by the end of the conversation when they initiate an interaction with a chatbot. This then influences the conversation's flow and topics to achieve the chosen goal. This can be exploited by developers since certain patterns of behavior tend to arise as a result. Therefore, the definition of a

chatbot adopted for this document is a computer program communicating by text in a humanly manner and who provides services to human users to accomplish a well-defined goal.

1.2 A brief history of chatbots

The first instance of a conversational agent was born in 1966: ELIZA was a computer program that simulated a psychiatrist and rephrased user input using basic (by today's standards) natural language processing techniques. Despite being relatively simple, the program managed to give the illusion of understanding the user's problems and successfully fooled a great many people. Its creator, Joseph Weizenbaum, even mentioned that his secretary would ask him to leave her so she could have a private conversation with ELIZA.

Then during several decades, chatbots heavily followed ELIZA's approach with minor additions brought into the field like speech synthesis and emotions management. Then in 2001 came Smarter Child, a conversational agent developed by Active Buddy, Inc. (now Colloquies) that operated on AOL Instant Messenger and MSN Messenger. Inspired by the rise of instant messaging platforms such as SMS, Smarter Child was created to provide quick access to news, weather forecasts, sports results, etc... The main innovation was that Smarter Child was connected to a knowledge base and detained useful information for its users. Unfortunately, the technical limitations of natural language processing caught up with bots on those platforms at the time and they were forgotten by History.

The next advancement for conversational agents was made by a team at IBM through the Watson AI project that has been in development since 2006. The agent was designed with the sole purpose of winning the American TV show Jeopardy! which it did in 2011 when competing against two of the show's former champions. Jeopardy! is interesting from an NLP point of view since the questions involve a lot of play on words and require fast information retrieval in vast knowledge bases. Unfortunately, this AI in its past form could only answer to one-liner questions and was unable to carry on a proper conversation with someone else.

Finally in the early 2010's came the rise of virtual assistants such as Apple's Siri, Microsoft's Cortana, Google's Google assistant, Amazon's Alexa and others. Those agents brought to the field the concept of conversation as well as goal-oriented dialog. Another major event in the field of chatbots was the release of the Messenger Platform

for Facebook Messenger in 2016 and allowed the creation of conversational agents for non-AI related companies.

As shown in this summary of the field of conversational agents, a lot of progress has been made since the early days of NLP. This does not imply however that current solutions are without flaws as will be highlighted in the next section.

1.3 Motivation

Several studies have been conducted studying user preferences concerning customer service. In particular, a recent survey done by Drift in collaboration with Survey-

Monkey Audience, Salesforce, and my clever assesses the image of chatbots in the eyes of the customers. It stems from the survey the following observations:

1. Customers experience problems with traditional online communication channels: 34% state that websites are hard to navigate, and 31% say that they can't get answers to simple questions through those communication vectors.
2. Customers see the following potential benefits in chatbot services: 24-hour service (64%), instant replies (55%), answers to simple questions (55%). It is clear that the customers' needs and expectations are not being fulfilled by traditional channels. They even see the perks of chatbots in comparison to other solutions.

However, despite all of this, they still feel that current chatbots are not as effective as they could be as observed in a survey conducted by Chatbots.org. Across all generations, 53% of customers view chatbots as "not effective" or only "somewhat effective". It highlights a discrepancy between the potential advantages of these methods and the actual implementations' capabilities. Nonetheless, when dividing the customers' impressions of chatbots by generations, it becomes clear that younger and more tech-savvy people are more optimistic regarding conversational agents. According to this survey, millennials and generation Z respectively rated chatbots as "effective" or "very effective" 56% and 54% of the time, whereas boomers and the silent generation respectively gave chatbots that rating only 38% and 49% of the time. All in all, this suggests that additional research and advancements be made in order to unlock conversational agents' full potential

1.4 Importance of Chatbot

Chatbots have become indispensable tools across industries, revolutionizing customer service and operational efficiency. Their round-the-clock availability ensures that businesses can provide immediate assistance to customers, improving response times and overall satisfaction. By automating routine tasks like answering FAQs and processing transactions, chatbots streamline operations, allowing human agents to focus on more complex issues and strategic initiatives. This scalability not only boosts productivity but also reduces operational costs, making chatbots a cost-effective solution for handling large volumes of customer interactions simultaneously.

Moreover, chatbots enhance user experiences through personalized interactions driven by AI and machine learning. By analyzing user data and preferences, chatbots deliver tailored responses and recommendations, fostering deeper engagement and loyalty. This data-driven approach not only improves customer satisfaction but also empowers businesses with valuable insights for refining products, services, and marketing strategies. Across e-commerce, healthcare, education, and beyond, chatbots play pivotal roles—from facilitating seamless shopping experiences and providing medical advice to supporting personalized learning journeys. With advancements in natural language processing, chatbots can engage in more natural and intuitive conversations, further enhancing their effectiveness in meeting diverse customer needs. As businesses continue to integrate AI-driven solutions, chatbots remain at the forefront of transforming customer service paradigms and driving operational excellence in the digital era.

CHAPTER 2

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this chapter will be formally introduced the theory behind the main problems in the conversational agents' field as well as the state-of-the-art machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques used in practice for chatbots.

2.1 High-level view of a conversational agent

Conceptually, a chatbot is composed of multiple components working in unison to accomplish a common goal. Figure 2.1 summarizes in visual form the relations between each part of a conversational agent. Upon reception of a new message, it is first processed by the language identification module. This can range from simple tag retrieval to more elaborate statistical methods. The new message, as well as the language and potential previous conversation messages retrieved from backend, are then fed to the intent classifier module whose role is to infer the intent the user is trying to convey.

Afterwards, the message's metadata, inferred intent and other information from backend will be used to determine an appropriate action or sequence of actions. For instance, a chatbot may decide to reply with a question if the intent is still not clear, or it could decide to reactivate a user account if the user's intention is to ask permission to reactivate his/her account.

Finally, the action handler module takes as input an action and properly executes said action. This is useful to implement it this way since a same action can be executed in different ways depending on the agent's environment. The way an action is performed can be completely different depending if the bot operates on the Messenger platform than on a company's website.

2.2 Language identification

Inferring the language of a text is sometimes a necessary first step in a larger natural language processing chain. Some languages even share homographs (e.g. room which appears both in English and Dutch even though it has a different meaning in each language) which may confuse algorithms with the semantics of these particular words hence requiring the need to identify the correct language for a given text before processing it further. In this work, the assumption that messages can only be written in a single language will be made; however, there are versions of this problem which involve detecting multiple languages in a single piece of text.

2.3 Intent classification

Upon receiving a new message, the conversational agent must be able to identify the goal the user is trying to accomplish. This is usually modelled as a multiclassification problem whose labels are the names of the possible user intentions. Techniques to solve this problem vary from simple keyword extraction to Bayesian inference to determine the user's request based on multiple messages. LSTM networks have been previously known to work well in this area. Those are used as well for the development of this project.

2.4 Knowledge management

An intelligent agent can only do so much without knowledge. The field concerned with allowing computers to handle knowledge has progressed significantly in the 1980's under the name of knowledge engineering. Early techniques involved usually an inference engine to manipulate facts and derive new knowledge using second and first order logic. It is a way of deriving answers to incomplete questions and are usually easily transcribed into API calls.

For conversational agents, knowledge engineering is extremely useful, for instance to answer basic questions about general facts. Siri and Amazon Alexa use internally knowledge inference methods to retrieve facts from the web and other sources (e.g. asking Alexa about trains departing from Brussels today might trigger an internal inference operation of the form train (Brussels; D; today) where D is an anonymous variable representing a destination).

Nowadays, knowledge management is mostly done through API calls and optimized database requests. Although more exotic methods inspired by graph-structured ontologies are used every now and then for knowledge bases

2.5 Problem background

With the fast development of technology and the increasing digitalization, there is a challenge to build relationships and trust among customers as they have the opportunity to choose from several organizations that provide the same or similar service or product (Jenneboer et al., 2022, p. 212). With the fast-paced technological improvements that are currently proceeding, it is increasingly important for businesses to embrace new technologies (Miklosik et al., 2019, p. 85705). Moreover, E-commerce in retail has been consistently growing in the last decade and is expected to continue growing from \$5.2 trillion in 2021 to approximately \$8.1 trillion in 2026 (Chevalier,

2022). This shows that it is important for organizations to ensure online service quality and meet customers' demands in the online environment. Customers perceive more risks and there is less trust from customers to be shopping online than in physical stores (Ariffin et al., 2018, p. 310). Thus, that creates a challenge for how organizations could build loyalty from their customers online.

CHAPTER 3

OBJECTIVES

Creating an objective for a chatbot Q&A can help guide its development and ensure it meets user needs effectively. Here's a structured objective for a chatbot designed for Q&A:

3.1 Purpose:

To provide users with accurate, timely, and helpful answers to their questions, enhancing their experience and satisfaction.

- 1) Accuracy:
 - a) Ensure the chatbot delivers correct and relevant information.
 - b) Continuously update the knowledge base to reflect the latest information.
- 2) User Engagement
 - a) Offer a conversational and user-friendly interface.
 - b) Maintain a tone and style appropriate to the user base.
- 3) Efficiency:
 - a) Provide quick responses to user queries.
 - b) Implement mechanisms to handle complex or ambiguous questions effectively.
- 4) Availability:
 - a) Operate 24/7 to assist users at any time.
 - b) Ensure high uptime and reliability.
- 5) Scalability:
 - a) Support a large number of simultaneous users without degradation in performance.
 - b) Adapt to increasing user demand and expanding question domains.
- 6) Learning and Adaptation:
 - a) Utilize user feedback to improve response quality.
 - b) Implement machine learning to enhance understanding and accuracy over time.
- 7) User Support and Escalation:
 - a) Provide clear instructions for users on how to interact with the chatbot.
 - b) Escalate queries to human support when necessary, ensuring a seamless transition.

8) Privacy and Security:

- a) Ensure user data privacy and comply with relevant data protection regulations.
- b) Implement robust security measures to protect against unauthorized access and data breaches.

3.2 Metrics for Success:

- User satisfaction ratings
- Response accuracy rate
- Average response time
- Number of queries handled without escalation
- User engagement levels
- Feedback and improvement cycle efficiency

3.3 Implementation Strategy

1. Knowledge Base Development

- Curate a comprehensive and up-to-date knowledge base.
- Regularly review and update content to ensure accuracy.

2. Natural Language Processing (NLP):

- Implement advanced NLP techniques to understand and process user queries.
- Continuously refine NLP models based on user interactions and feedback.

3. User Interface Design:

- Design an intuitive and accessible interface.
- Incorporate features like quick replies, suggested questions, and feedback options.

4. Testing and Iteration:

- Conduct thorough testing to identify and fix issues.
- Use A/B testing to determine the most effective interaction strategies.

5. Feedback Loop:

- Collect and analyze user feedback to guide improvements.
- Implement a system for users to report inaccuracies or issues easily.

By adhering to this objective, the chatbot can effectively serve users, providing valuable assistance and fostering a positive user experience.

3.4 Availability

One of the first attributes and benefits of AI Chatbots that comes to mind when compared to human service is their 24/7 availability. Furthermore, Jenneboer et al.

(2022, p. 215), describe availability as the chatbot being available anytime and everywhere. Chen et al. (2023), dissected this and made it into two different attributes which they called always available and omnipresence. This where always available refers to the fact that the chatbot never sleeps which means that customers can get the chatbot's service at any time (Chen et al., 2023). Omnipresence on the other hand means that the service from the chatbot is not limited by place and device (Chen et al., 2023). Availability from chatbots gives customers the benefit of being able to access services at all times and everywhere and at the same time reducing the effort in searching for a service (Chen et al., 2023). Continuing on this, Ariff et al. (2013, p. 472-473), conducted a study on e-service qualities and their impact on satisfaction and customer loyalty in the context of online banking. The results from the study showed that the availability of the e-service positivity affected satisfaction which has a positive relationship with customer loyalty (Ariff et al., 2013, p. 472-473). Thus, earlier studies imply that the availability of chatbots affects customer loyalty.

Therefore, we believe that this is a very important attribute of an AI chatbot in general, but also with the connection to customer loyalty. In addition to this, customers today expect organizations to always be available (Jenneboer et al., 2022, p. 226). This makes this attribute even more interesting to study in relation to customer loyalty for Gen Zs.

3.5 Ease of Use

The next attribute that we have chosen to adopt is the ease of use, which is an integral part of the technology acceptance model (TAM) which will be further explained below (see section 2.4). Davis (1989, p. 320), defined ease of use as the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort. Further, Davis (1989, p. 320), claims that if two applications are equal but one is perceived to be easier to use there is a greater chance for that application to be accepted by users. This is of importance for us in this thesis since for a technology to be able to create loyalty it first must be accepted. Chen et al. (2023), provided a simple definition of ease of use in the context of AI chatbots “The AI chatbot is easy to use”. While this may seem like a straightforward definition, it is a crucial aspect of chatbot usability, as the customer's perception of the application's ease of use ultimately determines its effectiveness. Additionally, according to Chen et al. (2023), the attribute of ease of use has benefits for customers as it reduces the customer learning cost and time spent learning how the

application works. Ashfaq et al. (2020), also used perceived ease of use as one of their attributes to evaluate AI chatbots, which shows the wide adoption of ease of use as an attribute of AI chatbots. Jenneboer et al. (2022, p. 215), had another name for ease of use and instead saw it as useability but with the same meaning as explained above. Furthermore, Van Der Goot & Pilgrim (2020, p. 177), found that a chatbot's ease of use can greatly affect customer experience if it's good, but if it is difficult to use, it can have a negative impact on the customer experience. Previous research has identified ease of use as an important aspect of AI chatbots (Chen et al, 2023), and that ease of use of chatbots positively influences the customer experience (Van Der Goot & Pilgrim, 2020, p. 177) which has a positive relation to customer loyalty. Therefore, we will adopt ease of use as one of the defining attributes of AI chatbots to study their relationship with customer loyalty.

CHAPTER 4

SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

This chapter will talk about the overall architecture of the conversational agent. More specifically, section 4.1 describes the agent's environment in details, section 4.2 will present the chatbot's class diagram, and section 4.3 will describe the agent's modules, what purpose they fulfil and how they accomplish it.

4.1 Agent environment

Figure 4.1: Agent environment model.

The agent environment consists of a few different parts. One of them is the user messages: they are a dynamic input that the agent can receive at any given time. They consist in a string representing the actual text sent by the user, and a metadata structure containing additional information like a pointer that links the message to the structure representing the particular conversation it belongs to, and possibly the time the message was sent, on which platform the message was sent, etc. The chatbot can only read the information it contains with no possible means of modifying it. Another significant part of the environment the agent has access to is the company's backend which contains additional information about the user and the database's state. The agent can both inspect and influence certain aspects of the backend. The chatbot also could send replies to the users to obtain new information, or simply to tell them that their request has been accepted and treated accordingly. A visual representation of the agent's environment is presented in Figure 4.1.

4.2 Class diagram

In this section, the connections between all the agent's modules will be highlighted and discussed. Figure 4.2 shows the class diagram of the agent's modules.

Figure 4.2: Chatbot class diagram.

As can be clearly seen from this diagram, the chatbot is made of several components each solving one problem. The component labelled **Client** at the top of the diagram is simply a generic client program that makes use of the chatbot. It can simply be a terminal client or a more complicated dynamic online listener that fetches new tickets when they are issued through the system.

The chatbot's 5 main components are:

- 1) Intent Classifier
- 2) Human Requester
- 3) Action Planner
- 4) Context Manager
- 5) Action Executor.

It is also shown that the **Action Planner** has access to 2 submodules, one of which (**Backend Interface**) being shared with another submodule.

4.3 System modules

This section will present the system's submodules by discussing their respective roles, and will also give their input as well as their outputs.

4.3.1 Intent classifier

This module is responsible for inferring the user intent based on a message. It heavily uses neural networks to perform its normal operation. Its only input is a single user message, and its output are a dictionary that maps every supported user intent with its corresponding probability for that message.

4.3.2 Human intervention requester

This module operates right after the intent classifier. Its role is to request the intervention of a human customer service agent in the case the intent of the user could not be identified correctly. It is provided as a module as it is easier to change between behaviors (For instance, one might want a more conservative chatbot when dealing with high profile customers that will request human intervention more often).

Its input is the whole context of a dialogue with a user, as provided by the context manager. Its output is simply a Boolean value which is true if the module judges that, given the context, human intervention is required; it returns false otherwise.

4.3.3 Context manager

The module whose role is to handle the structure which organizes contexts. A context in this case is defined as the sequence of messages, as well as metadata attached to them, which are useful for helping a user with a single problem. In human terms, this roughly corresponds to our intuitive concept of a single conversation/ticket.

4.3.4 Action planner

The action planner's goal is, given a probability vector, decide which actions the agent should take. It is responsible for observing the backends' state and generating a payload that contains the actions to perform and in which order. In this case, the payload's format will simply be a JSON object. It is also responsible for constructing the actual reply to be sent to the user. It makes use of two submodules: the locales handler and the backend interface.

4.4 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Within the increasing digitalization it has emerged new technologies. In particular communication and informational technologies (ICT) have increased the most during this time (Marangunic & Granic, 2015, p. 81). In 1986, Davis introduced the technology acceptance model (TAM) (Marangunic & Granic, 2015, p. 81). Marangunic & Granic (2015, p. 81), describes that Davis's model investigates how customers behave, and their attitudes towards acceptance or rejection of technology. Further, Marangunic & Granic (2015, p. 81) points out that the technology acceptance model (TAM), can be useful in understanding which factors of motivation mostly influence behavior when it comes to technology. This is because the basic principle of TAM is that when people use different IT devices, they make rational decisions when using IT (Kim et al., 2010, p. 311). According to Trivedi & Trivedi (2018, p. 172), TAM are capturing factors relating to service quality. Therefore, it is our belief that aspects of TAM will be of importance to us in this thesis. By looking further into TAM, Davis et al. (1989, p. 985), state that the technology acceptance model is divided into two dimensions. The first is perceived usefulness, which refers to the probability for a user to use the special technology that will increase their job performance within a company context. Secondly, perceived ease of use, means that the future user wants to be able to use the applications without any further effort (Davis et al., 1989, p. 985). Chen et al. (2021, p. 1524), integrates TAM and Information system success model and build a research model where they analyze the effects of chatbots on online customers, their satisfaction, and their experience. Chen et al. (2021, p. 1524), can see that there is a positive connection between the chatbot's usability and responsiveness and online customer experience. TAM has in many cases been related to usage in workplaces and in recent studies, it has shown that TAM has been used to increase the understanding of online behavior (Chiu et al., 2009, p. 348). Furthermore, the authors describe that there is importance in exploring the correlation between customer loyalty and TAM. Chiu et al. (2009, p. 357), describe that TAM can help to describe the behavior of customers that shop online. TAM can also create a deeper understanding of a customer's beliefs, and later on create loyalty among customers.

Therefore, we see TAM as a useful model, to underline the acceptance of technology. TAM is helpful for us in this thesis as it has helped create the ease-of-use attribute for AI chatbots. In addition to this, as AI chatbots are a quite new tool we

believe that the TAM model will be useful for us in our analysis. This since TAM can help predict how new technology will be accepted and therefore will support us in the analysis.

CHAPTER 5

SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter will justify the use of certain libraries for the project, as well as discuss the concrete implementation details of the completed system.

5.1 Programming language and libraries

Considering the context of the project and the company's software environment, the language Python was chosen as main programming language to implement the chatbot. This is a trade-off between ease of implementation due to the language's prolific machine learning catalogue, and the ease of use for future developers at GAMING1. Indeed, the company mainly works with the .NET framework and as such writes a significant amount of code in the C# language. However, Python is not a difficult language to learn and was deemed appropriate in this situation. Concerning libraries, there are a few used to implement the chatbot in practice. The first one is the Keras library whose overall goal is to provide a common and easy-to-use interface for several deep learning frameworks such as Tensorflow, Theano, etc ... The chatbot uses Keras on top of the Tensorflow library.

Another important library used is pandas which provides ways to efficiently store and organize datasets. It is useful for manipulating large amounts of data. Finally, a minor (relative to this project) but nevertheless important library is the scikit-learn library. It is used in this context for some utilities such as splitting a dataset into train validation and test sets.

5.2 Extracting data

The starting point is to be able to extract a messages dataset from the company's customer support system. Since the company started using Zendesk in 2013, there is a significant amount of data to retrieve from their database. There are a little more than 1,400,000 tickets present in total in their system as of the writing of this report. However, Zendesk unfortunately does not provide a means to export large number of tickets easily or at least not including the tickets' messages. Besides, it is easier to design a custom solution that can periodically export new tickets every week.

Therefore, a simple API crawler was designed to overcome this issue. The software is simply an infinite loop that requests ticket data in JSON format directly

from the Zendesk API 100 tickets at a time since that is the maximum number of tickets the API can send in one request. It first starts with a seed date which corresponds to the oldest date the crawler will extract tickets from. It will then process the remaining tickets in chronological order. Each time a batch of 100 tickets has been processed, the crawler requests what is called the next page of tickets to process. After a defined number of processed tickets, the crawler will save the current batch of tickets to disk to create a backup in case of failure. This is implemented because fully extracting tickets takes a non-negligible amount of time. If it does fail, the crawler looks for the last processed ticket in the backup file and restarts the process starting from that ticket. This mechanism is also used every time the crawler is launched making it possible to execute it every week or month to fetch new ticket data and update the model dynamically.

5.3 Generating responses

The approach outlined in Chapter 3 places significant emphasis on a retrieval-based method for generating responses, ensuring that interactions between the agent and the user remain non-offensive. This method not only safeguards the user experience but also aligns with best practices in automated customer service.

The core of this approach is the Action Planner module, which contains all the logic that is triggered when a user's intent is correctly identified. This module is crucial in maintaining the accuracy and relevance of the responses. For example, when a user inquiry about a delayed withdrawal, the Action Planner might call the backend system to check specific details. This could involve verifying that the user's account is in good standing and not blacklisted, or providing a detailed explanation if the delay is due to the transaction being processed through an international bank account.

The design of these responses is particularly meticulous. They are structured to closely resemble the communications one might expect from live customer support agents. This is intentional, as it ensures a consistent and professional tone that aligns with the formal nature of most customer service interactions. Given that the primary source of customer service inquiries is often formal emails, the responses generated by the system are crafted to match this format. They are detailed, polite, and provide clear and concise information to address the user's needs.

By adopting this approach, the maintainers can ensure a high level of user satisfaction. The retrieval-based method allows for the generation of responses that are

both accurate and contextually appropriate, reducing the risk of misunderstandings or offensive remarks. Additionally, by mirroring the formal style of customer service emails, the responses help in setting the right expectations and maintaining a professional interaction standard. This approach, therefore, not only enhances the effectiveness of automated customer support but also builds trust and reliability in the system.

5.4 GUI

Fig 5.4.1: Prototype Model 1

Fig 5.4.2: Prototype Model 2

5.5 Responsiveness

Our next AI chatbot attribute is responsiveness which has been used in numerous studies as an attribute or dimension of chatbots (Jenneboer et al., 2022; Trivedi, 2019; Li et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2021). Li et al. (2021, p. 579), defined responsiveness as the chatbot's capability to help and immediately provide service to users without delay in their response. In a study by Chen et al. (2021, p. 1512), they found that the responsiveness of chatbots had a positive influence on the customer experience in e-retailing. Responsiveness was first introduced as a dimension of human service agents in the SERVQUAL framework and was defined as the “willingness to help customers and provide prompt service” (Parasuaman et al., 1988, p. 39). Since then, as previously mentioned, responsiveness has been used in different contexts, as well as an AI chatbot attribute in several studies. Li et al. (2021, p. 583), argued that because AI chatbots are expected to act like human service agents, the dimension of responsiveness should be applicable to chatbots as well. Our argument to have this as one of our AI chatbot 15 attributes is similar. As responsiveness has been seen as an attribute of chatbots in several earlier studies that examines chatbots towards similar constructs as we are in this thesis (Li et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2021; Trivedi, 2019). Therefore, we agree with what Li et al. (2021, p. 583) stated, that this should be seen as an attribute of chatbots as they are supposed to act like human service agents.

5.6 Assurance

Similar to responsiveness, assurance was also first introduced as a dimension of service quality for human agents in the SERVQUAL framework where they defined it in the following way “Knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence” Parasuaman et al., 1988, p. 39). Assurance in the chatbot context refers to the chatbot's ability to build confidence in the user (Gorla et al., 2010, p. 213). A further explanation for assurance is that the chatbot is knowledgeable and maintains courteous communication with users (Gorla et al., 2010, p. 215). We can see how assurance is defined in the context of chatbots is similar to when it was originally defined towards human agents. Here we also have a similar argument as the one for responsiveness, because if AI chatbots are meant to mimic human service agents the attributes of a human service agent should be able to be applied to AI chatbots as well. Furthermore, assurance is an essential part of information systems like AI chatbots for provide good service quality (Trivedi, 2019, p. 96), and assurance is believed to be one of the most salient attributes of AI chatbots (Li et al., 2021, p. 579). This makes us

believe that it's very important to include this as one of the attributes of AI chatbots in this thesis. Beyond that Li et al. (2021, p. 593), concluded in their study, which examined what makes consumers continue to use AI chatbots in the travel agency, that assurance has a positive relation to continued use of chatbots and satisfaction. This again strengthens the argument that this could also have a positive impact on customer loyalty in a setting outside of travel agencies. Thus, we have chosen to include assurance as one of the attributes of AI chatbots in this thesis.

CHAPTER 6

WORKING

6.1 Standard Libraries

Logging:

Purpose: Used for tracking events that happen when some software runs. Logs are very useful for understanding program flow and for debugging.

Features: Different log levels (DEBUG, INFO, WARNING, ERROR, CRITICAL), configuration of log message formatting, multiple output destinations (console, file, etc.).

OS:

Purpose: Provides functions to interact with the operating system.

Features: File and directory manipulation, environment variable access, process management, and more.

RE:

Purpose: Regular expression operations.

Features: Pattern matching, searching, and replacing.

SHUTIL:

Purpose: High-level file operations.

Features: Copying, moving, renaming, and deleting files and directories.

TEMPFILE:

Purpose: Generate temporary files and directories.

Features: Creating temporary files/directories, which are cleaned up when they are no longer needed.

WARNINGS:

Purpose: Provide a way to issue warnings.

Features: Customizable warning messages, filtering, and controlling warnings.

RANDOM:

Purpose: Generate pseudorandom numbers.

Features: Random number generation, random selection, shuffling, and sampling.

6.2 Type Hinting

List, Dict, Any, Tuple, Optional, Union:

Purpose: Provide type hints in Python, which help in static type checking.

Features:

`List`: Represents a list of elements.

`Dict`: Represents a dictionary of key value pairs.

`Any`: Represents any type.

`Tuple`: Represents a fixed size, ordered collection of elements.

`Optional`: Represents an optional value (can be `None` or of a specified type).

`Union`: Represents a value that can be one of several types.

6.3 NLP Libraries

1. nltk (Natural Language Toolkit):

Purpose: Provides tools for working with human language data (text).

Features: Tokenization, parsing, classification, stemming, tagging, and more.

2. spacy:

Purpose: Industrialstrength NLP library.

Features: Tokenization, partofspeech tagging, named entity recognition, dependency parsing, and more. It is designed for largescale information extraction.

3. sentence_transformers:

Purpose: Provides easytouse BERTbased sentence and text embeddings.

Features: Pretrained models for generating sentence embeddings for various tasks like clustering or semantic search.

4. transformers:

Purpose: Provides stateoftheart generalpurpose architectures for NLP.

Features: Implementation of transformer models like BERT, GPT, etc., with pretrained models for a variety of tasks.

6.4 Data Handling

1. numpy:

Purpose: Fundamental package for scientific computing.

Features: Support for large, multidimensional arrays and matrices, mathematical functions, random number generation.

2. pandas:

Purpose: Data manipulation and analysis.

Features: Data structures like DataFrame for handling tabular data, operations for data cleaning, merging, reshaping, and more.

6.5 Web Framework

1. streamlit:

Purpose: Build and share data applications.

Features: Turns Python scripts into interactive apps, supports widgets, Realtime updates, and easy deployment.

6.6 Image and Document Processing

1. PIL (Pillow):

Purpose: Image processing.

Features: Opening, manipulating, and saving many different images file formats.

2. PyPDF2:

Purpose: PDF file manipulation.

Features: Splitting, merging, cropping, and transforming PDF files.

3. docx:

Purpose: Create and update Microsoft Word `.docx` files.

Features: Reading, writing, and modifying Word documents.

6.7 Sentiment Analysis

1. vaderSentiment:

Purpose: Sentiment analysis specifically for social media texts.

Features: Rule based sentiment analysis with a focus on polarity (positive/negative) and intensity.

6.8 OCR (Optical Character Recognition)

1. pytesseract:

Purpose: Optical character recognition tool for extracting text from images.

Features: Wrapper for Google's TesseractOCR Engine, supports multiple languages, and can handle various image formats.

These libraries provide a robust set of tools for a wide range of tasks, from data manipulation and machine learning to web development and image processing.

6.9 File Paths

1. `LOG_FILE_PATH`: This is the path where your log file will be stored. Logging is essential for tracking the flow of your application and debugging issues.

2. `UPLOAD_FOLDER`: This directory will be used to store uploaded files. Ensuring this directory exists is crucial to avoid errors when files are uploaded.

3. `TEMP_FOLDER`: This directory will be used for temporary files. Temporary files might be needed for intermediate storage during processing tasks.

6.10 Model Names

1. `MODEL_NAMES`: This likely contains the names or identifiers of models you will be using in your application. These could be machine learning models or NLP models.

6.11 Threshold

1. `DEFAULT_SIMILARITY_THRESHOLD`: This is a predefined value used to determine similarity in your application. For instance, in NLP tasks, it might be used to determine if two sentences are similar enough based on cosine similarity or another metric.

6.12 Setup Tasks

1. Create Directories: Ensure `'UPLOAD_FOLDER'` exists.

To ensure that the `'UPLOAD_FOLDER'` exists, we can use the `'os'` library to check if the directory exists, and if not, create it.

2. Configure Warnings and Logging: Set up logging configurations and filter specific warnings.

Logging configurations ensure that all important events in your application are tracked. You can configure the logging level, format, and file handler. Filtering warnings helps in ignoring specific warning messages that you are aware of and have deemed noncritical.

Explanation

1. Creating Directories:

The script checks if `'UPLOAD_FOLDER'` and `'TEMP_FOLDER'` exist using `'os.path.exists()'`.

If they do not exist, `'os.makedirs()'` is called to create them. This ensures your application has the necessary directories for file handling.

2. Configuring Logging:

The `'logging.basicConfig()'` function is used to set up the logging configuration. It sets the logging level to `'DEBUG'`, which means all messages (DEBUG and higher) will be logged. The format for the log messages is specified.

Handlers are added to output log messages to a file (`'FileHandler'`) and to the console (`'StreamHandler'`).

3. Filtering Warnings:

The `'warnings.filterwarnings()'` function is used to ignore `'DeprecationWarning'` and `'UserWarning'` categories.

This helps in keeping the console output clean and focusing only on important warnings.

This setup ensures that your application is ready to handle file uploads, log important events, and filter out unnecessary warnings.

6.13 Custom Exceptions

Custom exceptions provide a way to handle specific error scenarios in a more controlled and descriptive manner. This makes the code easier to debug and maintain. Here are the custom exceptions for the specific error scenarios mentioned:

1. `FileProcessingError`: Raised when there is an error in processing files.
2. `ModelLoadingError`: Raised when there is an error in loading models.
3. `AnalysisError`: Raised when there is an error during analysis.
4. `UnsupportedFileTypeError`: Raised when an unsupported file type is encountered.

6.11 Model Loading

NLP models and tools:

1. `spaCy Model`: Used for general NLP tasks such as tokenization, part of speech tagging, and named entity recognition.
2. `SentenceTransformer`: Used for generating sentence embeddings, which can be used for tasks like clustering, semantic search, and similarity comparison.
3. `NER Pipeline`: Used for named entity recognition, which identifies entities in text such as people, organizations, and locations.

Explanation

1. Custom Exceptions:

Four custom exceptions (`FileProcessingError`, `ModelLoadingError`, `AnalysisError`, `UnsupportedFileTypeError`) are defined, each with a default message.

These exceptions provide clear and specific error messages, making it easier to understand what went wrong.

2. Model Loading Functions:

`load_spacy_model(model_name)` Attempts to load a spaCy model and raises a `ModelLoadingError` if it fails.

`load_sentence_transformer(model_name)` Attempts to load a SentenceTransformer model and raises a `ModelLoadingError` if it fails.

`load_ner_pipeline(model_name)` Attempts to load a named entity recognition pipeline using the Hugging Face transformers library and raises a `ModelLoadingError` if it fails.

3. Model Loading:

Each model loading function is called within a `tryexcept` block. If a model fails to load, the corresponding custom exception is caught, and an error message is printed.

If a model loads successfully, a success message is printed.

By using custom exceptions and structured model loading functions, you can handle errors gracefully and provide clear, actionable error messages, improving the robustness and maintainability of your code.

Custom exceptions are specialized error classes that you define in your application to handle specific error scenarios in a more controlled and meaningful way. By defining custom exceptions, you can provide more detailed and context specific error messages, which can greatly aid in debugging and maintaining your code. Here's an explanation of the custom exceptions you mentioned:

6.14 Explanation and Use Cases

1. FileProcessingError:

Scenario: You have a function that processes uploaded files (e.g., reading content from a text file or parsing a PDF). If an error occurs during this process (like a file not being found or failing to read due to incorrect format), raising a `FileProcessingError` provides a clear indication that the problem is related to file handling.

2. ModelLoadingError:

Scenario: When loading machine learning models, if a model file is corrupted, missing, or incompatible with the current version of the software, a `ModelLoadingError` should be raised to indicate that the problem occurred during the model loading phase.

3. AnalysisError:

Scenario: During data analysis or execution of algorithms, unexpected issues such as invalid input data, calculation errors, or other logical problems might occur. Raising an `AnalysisError` provides a clear message that the issue is within the analysis logic.

4. **UnsupportedFileTypeError:**

Scenario: When the application supports specific file types (e.g., only .txt and .pdf files), and the user tries to upload a .jpg file, raising an `UnsupportedFileTypeError` can be used to inform the user and handle the error gracefully.

6.15 Benefits of Using Custom Exceptions

Clarity: Custom exceptions provide clear and specific error messages that can help identify the exact source of the error.

Maintainability: Code is easier to maintain and debug when errors are well categorized.

Error Handling: Allows for more precise error handling and recovery mechanisms, improving the robustness of the application.

By defining and using these custom exceptions, you ensure that your application can handle specific error scenarios gracefully and provide meaningful feedback to developers and users.

Loading various NLP models and tools involves initializing and configuring models for specific tasks such as tokenization, sentence embeddings, and named entity recognition (NER). Here's a detailed explanation of each model and how to load them:

1. **spaCy Model**

Purpose: spaCy is a popular NLP library designed for fast and efficient processing of large text corpora. It supports various NLP tasks like tokenization, part of speech tagging, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition.

2. **SentenceTransformer**

Purpose: SentenceTransformers is a library that provides easy-to-use BERT-based and other transformer-based models to generate sentence and text embeddings. These embeddings can be used for various applications like clustering, semantic search, and sentence similarity.

3. **NER Pipeline**

Purpose: Named Entity Recognition (NER) is the process of identifying and classifying named entities (like people, organizations, locations) in text. The Hugging Face Transformers library provides pretrained models and pipelines for performing NER.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION

In this thesis, we have embarked on a comprehensive journey to develop an intelligent chatbot using AI and ML technologies. The process began with defining the goals and constraints of the chatbot in Chapter 3, followed by designing a scalable software solution in Chapter 4. This solution was capable of dynamically extracting and labeling ticket data from an existing Zendesk environment, as discussed in Chapter 5.

The chatbot's architecture was meticulously broken down into various modules, some of which employed neural network models. These models' structures and properties were extensively analyzed in Chapter 6, and an innovative approach using Bayes' rule was introduced to allow users to clarify their inputs. Chapter 7 showcased the final results of the chatbot, presenting performance metrics and a manual testing method.

The developed solution proves to be effective and adaptable, offering easy deployment and development opportunities across different systems supporting Python environments. The chatbot can be extended to support additional languages and address various user problems, although future maintainers should be aware of potential edge cases where the chatbot may not perform optimally.

7.1 Future Scope

Automated Data Extraction: Data from unstructured documents, like contracts, invoices, and receipts, can be automatically extracted using chatbots designed for document analysis. This skill is particularly useful in fields where processing massive amounts of papers can be laborious and prone to errors, such as finance, insurance, and legal services.

Retrieving and Searching Information: Chatbots that possess document analysis skills are able to effectively search and retrieve information from vast document libraries. This is advantageous in fields where prompt access to precise information is essential, such as healthcare, research, and education.

Compliance and Regulatory Requirements: Document analysis chatbots can help guarantee that papers meet regulatory standards in industries like healthcare, banking, and law that are subject to tight regulatory compliance. By pointing out discrepancies, mistakes, or missing data, these chatbots help lower compliance risks.

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